

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AZNIZAN****FIRST NAME: AZIZA****PROGRAM CODE: DDIA****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 6%

The author used the following software: MS Word -2019 Office 365 on macOS 13.3.1 (22E261)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Consider the following scenarios:

I. Maria, a researcher, reads a study on the relationship between climate change and human behavior. She then writes her article on the topic, using her own words but basing most of her findings on the original study. She does not mention the original research in her writing.

II. James, a student, includes a lengthy quote from a book in his essay. The selection is more than four lines long, so he indents it and does not use quotation marks. He does not provide a citation for the quote.

III. Olivia, a journalist, writes an article on the well-known fact that smoking causes lung cancer. She doesn't provide any citations in her article.

IV. Sam, a student, paraphrases a paragraph from a book in his assignment. He uses his own words and writing style but provides the same information as the original paragraph. He does not cite the source.

Which of the following scenarios describes plagiarism?¹

- Only I and II, and IV.**
- Only II and IV.
- Only I and II.
- All of the above.

2. How do style guides contribute to the coherence and consistency of a publication, and what aspects of writing do they typically encompass?²

- Style guides contribute to consistency and coherence by standardizing various elements such as voice, terminology, paragraph indentation, headings, abbreviations, and branding.**
- Style guides ensure coherence and consistency by enforcing grammatical rules and the correct use of punctuation, focusing primarily on sentence structure and grammar.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34.

² *Ibid.*, 41-42.

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- Style guides contribute to coherence by dictating the type of vocabulary to be used, focusing mainly on language use and terminology.
 - Style guides ensure consistency by directing the choice of topics and the depth of their treatment, primarily focusing on content creation.
3. Which of the following best describes the relationship between a warrant and its relevance to a research argument in an academic context?³
- A warrant is used when the researcher anticipates that the reader might reject the claim due to the perceived irrelevance of the supporting reasons. It explains why the truth of the reason supports the validity of the claim.**
 - A warrant is necessary only when the claim's validity is in question. It bridges any understanding gap and clarifies any potential misconceptions about the claim.
 - A warrant is only used when a researcher wants to strengthen further a claim that has already been substantiated with ample evidence. It serves merely as an auxiliary support system.
 - Warrants are necessary for every research argument. With them, the argument would be regarded as complete and supported.
4. Which of the following is NOT a recommended practice when preparing notes for an oral presentation according to Turabian's Rule of Style?⁴
- Writing out your notes as complete sentences that you can read aloud.**

³ [Ibid., 61-62.](#)

⁴ [Ibid., 132.](#)

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- Creating your notes from scratch, rather than cutting and pasting from a written text.
 - Using a separate page for each main point.
 - Visually highlighting main points for instant recognition during the presentation.
5. Which two citation styles are covered in Turabian's Rule of Style?⁵
- Notes-bibliography style and author-date style.**
 - MLA and APA styles.
 - APA and Harvard styles.
 - Chicago style and MLA styles.
6. According to Turabian's Rule of Style, which of the following statements is true regarding line breaks within words? Choose the correct option from the four plausible answers provided below.⁶
- Line breaks within words should be avoided unless manually inserted with optional hyphens.**
 - Line breaks within words are allowed, especially when using full justification in the document.
 - Line breaks within words are only acceptable for compound words formed with prefixes.

⁵ [Jbid.](#), 141-142.

⁶ [Jbid.](#), 312-313.

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- The word processor's automatic hyphenation feature should determine line breaks within words.
7. Which qualitative research paradigm emphasizes the integration of research and action, seeks to bring about social change and address inequality and social justice issues, and involves active collaboration with research participants?⁷
- Critical Theory.**
- Postpositivism.
- Pragmatism.
- Social Constructivism/Interpretivism.
8. When writing a literature review, what is the key difference between synthesis and summary?⁸
- Synthesis combines and contrasts information from different sources, while summary collates and restates information.**
- Synthesis focuses on providing a cursory overview, while summary addresses distinct sets of information.
- Synthesis presents a comprehensive understanding and extends new lines of thinking, while summary captures the literal meaning of texts.

⁷ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*, 4th ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 150.

⁸ [Ibid., 385.](#)

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Synthesis pulls together and lists essential points, while summary highlights important issues of connection and relatedness.

9. What is the correct punctuation mark to indicate an omission in the text, and how should it be placed?⁹

Ellipsis points (...) with a final full stop if followed by another punctuation mark.

Semicolon (;) to indicate an omission in the text.

Forward slash (/) to indicate an omission in the text.

Hyphen (-) to indicate an omission in the text.

10. Which treaty extended qualified majority voting to new areas and established the role of the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy?¹⁰

The Treaty of Lisbon.

The Merger Treaty.

The Treaty of Amsterdam.

The Treaty of Nice.

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⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide*, 8th ed. (Brussels: Publications Office of the European Union, 2021), 9.

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¹⁰ [Ibid.](#), 77.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Euclid University, 2021.

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Turabian, Kate L., Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, and William T. Fitzgerald. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth ed. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

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Bloomberg, Linda D., and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.